

Outer-sphere Ion Association and Thermodynamics of some Bis(1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)copper(II) Complexes

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The ion-association of $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]^{2+}$ (AMUH = 1-amidino-*O*-methylurea and AEUH = 1-amidino-*O*-methylurea with Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and NO_3^- was investigated at 18, 25 and 35° by means of conductivity measurement in aqueous solutions. The order in magnitude of the ion-association (K_A) was $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{I}^-$, and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]^{2+} > [\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]^{2+}$. The thermodynamic functions have been calculated. Using Bjerrum equation, Stoke's law and Dennison-Ramsey theory the respective sizes of the ion-pairs have also been evaluated and compared.

Conductivity measurements over a wide temperature range for electrolyte solutions can provide detailed information concerning ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions, especially from thermodynamic viewpoint¹⁻⁵. Outer-sphere ion-association of some transition metal complexes containing trivalent central metal ions have been studied conductometrically by various worker^{1,5-17}. Literature shows that very little work has been done on ion-pair formation of transition metal complexes containing bivalent central metal ions, and this is more so in the case of copper(II) complexes. Recently, Yokoyama and his coworkers¹⁸ have studied conductometrically the temperature-dependence of hydrophobic ion-association of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) ion with aren-disulphonate ions in water.

The present work deals with the electric conductivities and ion-pair formation of bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)-, bis(1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea)copper(II) halides and nitrates in aqueous solution at 18, 25 and 35 ± 0.1°. From the values of association constants of these complexes at different temperatures, the thermodynamic functions can be estimated which to understand the nature of ion-association. The sizes of ion-pairs as evaluated from Bjerrum equation, Stoke's law and Dennison-Ramsey theory have also been compared.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity data : From the observed equivalent conductivities (Λ_{exp}) of the complexes¹⁹ at various

concentrations, the limiting equivalent conductivity (Λ_{ops}^0) of the complexes were determined by Onsager method of extrapolation²⁰, and whence the limiting conductivity of complex cations were available (Table 1, Fig. 1). The deviation of the Λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$ plot from the theoretical Onsager line, i.e. plot of Λ ($= \Lambda_{\text{ons}}^0 - bC^{1/2}$) vs $C^{1/2}$ (Figs. 2 and 3) is considered to be due to the outer-sphere association of the complex cation and the anion. The analysis was carried out in a similar manner as employed by Jenkins and Monk⁹ and other workers^{10-12, 17,21} assuming the following ion-pair formation,

(AAUH = 1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)

where the triple-ion formation was regarded as being negligible in the dilute solutions investigated. The experimental solution is taken as mixture of 2 : 1 of molar concentration αm and 1 : 1 valent salt, i.e. $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AAUH})_2]\text{X}\}^+$, X^- of molar concentration $(1-\alpha)m$. Here α is the degree of dissociation of the ion-pair and m the molar concentration of the salt. The Onsager equations for 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 valent salts of the complexes are set up in the general form,

$$\Lambda_{\text{exp}} = \Lambda_{\text{ons}}^0 - bI^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

in which b is the theoretical slope, and I the ionic strength is given by the relation,

Fig 1 Onsager extrapolation at 25° (a) [Cu(AMUH)₂]Cl₂, (b) [Cu(AMUH)₂]Br₂, (c) [Cu(AMUH)₂]I₂, (d) [Cu(AMUH)₂](NO₃)₂, (e) [Cu(AEUH)₂]Cl₂, (f) [Cu(AEUH)₂]Br₂, (g) [Cu(AEUH)₂]I₂ and (h) [Cu(AEUH)₂](NO₃)₂

$$l = 1/2(1+2\alpha)C \quad (3)$$

where C is in equivalent per litre. The Λ^0 values of the ion pair, $\{[Cu(AAUH)_2]X\}^+$ may be taken as one-half^{10,12} of the bivalent ion $[Cu(AAUH)_2]^{2+}$. The equivalent conductivity of the solution mixture is given by

$$\Lambda_{exp} = \alpha\Lambda_{21} + 1/2 (1-\alpha) \Lambda_{11} \quad (4)$$

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 25°

Compd	Λ_{app}^0	Λ_{ons}^0	Λ^0	Λ_1 (Mean)
I [Cu(AMUH) ₂]Cl ₂	123.19	120.09	43.64	43.21
[Cu(AMUH) ₂]Br ₂	124.07	121.58	43.48	
[Cu(AMUH) ₂]I ₂	122.56	120.45	43.65	
[Cu(AMUH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	115.50	113.37	42.07	
II [Cu(AEUH) ₂]Cl ₂	109.54	107.07	30.73	41.93
[Cu(AEUH) ₂]Br ₂	125.14	122.22	44.12	
[Cu(AEUH) ₂]I ₂	121.34	122.65	45.85	
[Cu(AEUH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	120.44	118.49	47.02	

Fig 2 Evaluation of Λ_{app}^0 and theoretical line for (a) [Cu(AMUH)₂]Cl₂, (b) [Cu(AMUH)₂]Br₂, (c) [Cu(AMUH)₂]I₂ and (d) [Cu(AMUH)₂](NO₃)₂ at 25° upper line shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{ons} - bC^{1/2})$ vs $C^{1/2}$ lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$

Fig 3 Evaluation of Λ_{app}^0 and theoretical line for (a) [Cu(AEUH)₂]Cl₂, (b) [Cu(AEUH)₂]Br₂, (c) [Cu(AEUH)₂]I₂ and (d) [Cu(AEUH)₂](NO₃)₂ at 25° upper line shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{ons} - bC^{1/2})$ vs $C^{1/2}$ lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$

Starting with the value of α as 1 in equation (3) and substituting the corresponding value of l in equation (4), a truer value of α is obtained, which is again fed into equation (3) and this way the cycle is repeated till the constant value of α is obtained. The dissociation constant (K) of the ion-pair (equation 1) is calculated from the equation.

$$K = \frac{[X^-][Cu(AAUH)_2]^{2+}}{[Cu(AAUH)_2]X^+} = \frac{(1+\alpha)\alpha m f_1 f_3}{(1-\alpha)f_2} \quad (5)$$

where f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are activity coefficients of the species X^- , $\{[Cu(AAUH)_2]X\}^+$ and $[Cu-(AAUH)_2]^{2+}$ respectively, and can be evaluated from Debye-Huckel limiting equation²²,

$$-\log f_1 = 0.509 Z_1^2 I^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where f_1 refers to the activity coefficient of the Z_1 ion. The computed values of association constants ($K_A = 1/K$) for bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)copper(II) and bis(1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea)copper(II) chloride, bromide, iodide and nitrate are given in Table 2, and follow the order (i) $\{[Cu(AMUH)_2]Cl\}^+ > \{[Cu(AMUH)_2]Br\}^+ > \{[Cu(AMUH)_2]NO_3\}^+ > \{[Cu(AMUH)_2]I\}^+$, (ii) $\{[Cu(AEUH)_2]Cl\}^+ > \{[Cu(AEUH)_2]Br\}^+ > \{[Cu(AEUH)_2]NO_3\}^+ > \{[Cu(AEUH)_2]I\}^+$ and (iii) $\{[Cu(AMUH)_2]X\}^+ > \{[Cu(AEUH)_2]X\}^+$. The trends are in agreement with those values of analogous series in trivalent metal complexes^{5,9,12,16}. It could be explained in terms of solvation concept and H-bonding as explained in the earlier work^{16,23}. The association constant was also found to increase with decreasing size of the ligand in the coordination sphere.

Thermodynamic parameters The changes in the free energy (ΔG^0) for complexes have been calculated from the association constants of the ion-pairs using the formula, $\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_A$. Enthalpy change (ΔH) can be evaluated from the slope of the linear plots

Fig 4 Plots of $\log K_A$ vs T^{-1} (a) $[Cu(AMUH)_2]Cl_2$ (b) $[Cu(AMUH)_2]Br_2$, (c) $[Cu(AMUH)_2]I_2$, (d) $[Cu(AMUH)_2](NO_3)_2$ (e) $[Cu(AEUH)_2]Cl$, (f) $[Cu(AEUH)_2]Br$, (g) $[Cu(AEUH)_2]I$ and (h) $[Cu(AEUH)_2](NO_3)_2$ slope = $-\Delta H/19.5$

of $\log K_A$ against $1/T$ (Fig 4). The entropy change (ΔS^0) has been calculated from the relation, $\Delta S^0 = (\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0)/T$, which is found to decrease very slightly with rise in temperature (Table 2). A positive entropy change has been explained on the assumption that the iceberg⁹ structure around the complex cation and anion is broken when ion-association takes, leading to a greater degree of disorder. Dey and Dutta¹³ suggested that with increase in temperature, such effects are responsible for increase in association constant values and consequently in entropy changes in tris(biguanide)cobalt(III) salts. But in the present case, a reverse observation is found. This can be interpreted by assuming that the breaking up of the solvent structure around the complex cation and anion (forming the ion-pair) is not the predominant phenomenon. The system under investigation may be treated to have obeyed the simple law of increasing dissociation with rise in temperature. Similar conclusion has been drawn by Mishra and Singh¹⁷ in their work on tris(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole)chromium(III) salts in aqueous solutions.

TABLE 2—ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEX

Ion pair	Temp K	K_A	$-\Delta G$ KJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH KJ K ⁻¹	ΔS JK mol ⁻¹	
I $\{[Cu(AMUH)_2]Cl\}^+$	291	72.80	10.38		78.06	
	298	63.50	10.29	12.34	75.94	
	304	53.85	10.22		74.11	
	$\{[Cu(AMUH)_2]Br\}^+$	291	63.90	10.06		91.10
		298	52.50	9.82	16.45	88.15
		304	42.00	9.57		84.49
	$\{[Cu(AMUH)_2]I\}^+$	291	44.74	9.20		82.54
		298	37.85	9.07	14.82	80.1
		304	30.10	9.31		78.34
	$\{[Cu(AMUH)_2](NO_3)\}^+$	291	59.57	9.89		87.63
		298	48.13	9.60	15.61	84.60
		304	39.10	9.31		80.91
II $\{[Cu(AEUH)_2]Cl\}^+$	291	67.76	10.20		97.60	
	298	55.65	9.96	18.20	94.50	
	304	43.10	9.64		90.39	
	$\{[Cu(AEUH)_2]Br\}^+$	291	61.42	9.96		111.27
		298	45.58	9.40	22.42	106.78
		304	33.54	9.00		102.01
	$\{[Cu(AEUH)_2]I\}^+$	291	37.35	8.76		77.42
		298	30.57	8.47	13.77	74.63
		304	25.11	8.26		71.53
	$\{[Cu(AEUH)_2](NO_3)\}^+$	291	54.95	9.70		107.35
		298	41.18	9.21	21.54	103.19
		304	30.30	8.74		98.31

Sizes of ion-pairs The limiting conductivity

of $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]^{2+}$ ions directly gives ionic radius (a) through Stoke's law²⁵,

$$a = \frac{9.16 \times 10^{-7} Z_i}{\Lambda_i^0} \quad (7)$$

where Z_i is the valency of the i -th ion and Λ_i^0 is the limiting conductivity of the i -th ion. The radii of the ion-pairs are equal to the sum of the Stoke's radii of the complex cation and the anion. Expectedly, the complex cation $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]^{2+}$ (4.37Å) is greater than that of $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]^{2+}$ (4.24 Å) which is accordance with the size of the ligand.

The sizes of the ion-pairs have also been evaluated from their association constants by using Bjerrum relationship²⁶.

$$K_A = \frac{4\pi N}{1000} \left(\frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{DkT} \right)^3 Q(b) \quad (8)$$

where, $b = (Z_1|Z_2|e^2)/aDkT$, a being the distance of the closest approach of the ions forming the ion-pair. From the experimental association constants K_A , the value of b was then evaluated from $Q(b)$ values using the standard table²⁷, and hence the value of a could be obtained.

Denison and Ramsey²⁸ also suggested the relationship between K_A and size of the ion-pair as

$$\ln K_A = \frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{aDkT} \quad (9)$$

the symbols having the same meaning as earlier. The sizes of ion-pairs as calculated from Stoke's equation, Bjerrum equation and Denison-Ramsey have been compared (Table 3). The three results do not agree well, such deviations between Bjerrum and Stoke's law was also reported by Jenkins and Monk⁹ for Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ion associates with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_6]^{3+}$, by De and Dutta¹² for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and SO_4^{2-} ion associates with $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$, Mishra and Singh¹⁷ for Cl^- , Br^- and NO_3^- ion associates with $[\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3]^{3+}$ (GBH = guanidinumbenzimidazole) and Rajmuhon *et al.*^{16,23} for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and SO_4^{2-} ion associates with $[\text{Co}(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(2,2\text{'-dipy})(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(1,10\text{-phen})(\text{AAUH})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{glyH})(\text{AAUH})_2]^{2+}$.

Experimental

The chloride, bromide, iodide and nitrate salts of bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)- and bis(1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea)copper(II) were prepared following the reported procedure²⁹. The complexes were carefully recrystallised from hot water and purity was examined through conventional elemental analysis and spectral measurements. The results were in good agreement with those of the literature values (as shown in parentheses); the percentage composition of the elements and water are : $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ [Cu, 17.12 (17.32), N, 30.62 (30.57), Cl, 19.01 (19.37)]; $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}_2$ [Cu, 13.21(13.21), N, 24.71 (24.64), Br, 34.99 (35.13)]; $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}_2$ [Cu, 11.21 (11.51), N, 20.30 (20.39), I, 46.31 (46.16)]; $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ [Cu, 15.01 (15.13), N, 34.01 (33.82)]; $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Cu, 15.01 (15.06), N, 26.31 (26.57), Cl, 16.91 (16.84), H_2O , 6.72 (6.41)]; $[\text{Co}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Cu, 12.61 (12.22), N, 21.32 (21.55), Br, 30.46 (30.75), H_2O , 6.12 (6.22)]; $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}_2$ [Cu, 10.62 (10.62), N, 19.42 (19.31), I, 43.12 (43.98)]; $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Cu, 13.21 (13.86), N, 30.12 (30.58), H_2O , 3.12 (3.93)].

TABLE 3—IONIC RADII OF CATION/ANION/ION-PAIR OF THE COMPLEXES

Cation/Anion/ Ion-pair	Radius from Stoke's law Å	Radius from Bjerrum eqn Å	Radius from Denison-Ramsey Å
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]^{2+}$	4.24		
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]^{2+}$	4.37		
Cl^-	1.20		
Br^-	1.18		
I^-	1.19		
NO_3^-	1.28		
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^+$	5.44	1.60	3.45
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^+$	5.42	1.72	3.63
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}\}^+$	5.43	1.85	3.89
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{NO}_3)\}^+$	5.52	1.74	3.70
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^+$	5.57	1.67	3.56
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^+$	5.55	1.76	3.74
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}\}^+$	5.56	1.68	4.18
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{NO}_3\}^+$	5.65	1.80	3.78

The conductivity of the complexes at different concentrations was measured at 1 kHz with a D.D.R. conductivity meter (Systronic 304). The thermal equilibrium was made on a Haake Mess-technik D8-6 thermostat. The conductivity meas-

urement for each sample (solution) was accomplished within 5 h after the preparation of the solution in order that the dissociation of the complex ion itself is neglected for the conductivity of the solvent also.

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